

Hydration Energies of Gas Phase Polyatomic Ions and Molecules—A CNDO/2 Approach

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The published results of *ab initio* calculations of solvation energies¹ of a number of species lead to certain general trends with the help of which many of the energy components occurring in the Daudel's symbolic expression² for hydration energy can be estimated. This feature, coupled with Born's free energy of transfer from vacuum to solvent medium within the frame work of CNDO/2 molecular orbital charge distribution, enables the calculation of hydration energy. Radius adjustment, which is an accessory encumbrance in any electrochemical calculation, is made in a very general manner.

THE problem of solvation and free energy changes on transfer of ions from one dielectric medium to another has been probed theoretically and experimentally³. Attempts at formulation of expressions of hydration energies have been made at various levels of sophistication. Previous relations⁴⁻⁸ have invariably been accompanied, in practice, by assumptions of (i) increased value of the radius on hydration, (ii) discrete or continuum nature of the dielectric environment permitting the use of adjusted dichotomy or nondichotomy of dielectric constant values, and (iii) in many cases, the stereodispositions of the hydration ligands^{5,6} and the interatomic distances. More recent formulations, falling within the area of quantum mechanical self consistent field theories, involve 'supermolecule' approach¹, local field theories⁹, 'solvaton' approach¹⁰ and perturbation effect due to polarisability of the environment¹¹.

Our approach is an adaptation of Hoijtink *et al.*¹² within the framework of CNDO/2 m.o. theory for calculation of the main contribution towards the hydration energy of gas phase polyatomic ions or molecules. The total hydration energy break-up (Daudel²) is given as

$$\epsilon_s = \epsilon_{s,c} + \epsilon_{s,o} + (\epsilon_{s,e} + \epsilon_{s,p} + \epsilon_{s,d}) + \epsilon_{s,a} \quad (1)$$

where $\epsilon_{s,c}$ = Cavitation energy, during solvation.

$\epsilon_{s,o}$ = Energy of partial orientation of solvent molecules not in the primary solvation sheath.

$\epsilon_{s,e}$, $\epsilon_{s,p}$ and $\epsilon_{s,d}$ = Electrostatic interaction energies of charging, polarisation of the environment and dispersion energy, respectively.

$\epsilon_{s,a}$ = Anisotropic interaction energy in solvation responsible for dipolar binding of solvent molecules at localised points of the solute = primary hydration energy.

The present method consists of the following steps.

1. The CNDO/2 technique¹³ is employed to find the resultant net atomic charge distributions in the ions or molecules¹ in the gaseous state with the individual radii values, r_i 's and interatomic distances, r_{ij} 's.

2(a). We shall treat water-cluster to consist of tetrahedron of five water molecules as has very often been used in the past. A tetrahedron is first dissociated into five water molecules (energy ϵ_1 per molecule) and 'n' number out of these five, necessary for primary hydration of each solute (ion or molecule) are evaporated (energy ϵ_2 per molecule) to create a cavity in the bulk. The remaining (5-n) molecules participate in tetrahedral formation with the rest of the bulk solvent causing an exothermic energy of binding ϵ_3 per molecule. Thus, $5\epsilon_1 + n\epsilon_2 + (5-n)\epsilon_3 = \epsilon_{s,c}$ of Daudel expression (equation 1).

(b). The solute molecule (or ion) in the gaseous equilibrium configuration is approached by 'n' number of H₂O molecules to form a hydrated species in gas phase state. The energy involvement will be ϵ_4 (exothermic) and is identifiable with $\epsilon_{s,a}$ of equation 1.

(c). During such exothermic interactions, there will be some polarisation of charges in the gas phase species accompanied by dilations of bonds. The endothermic energy involvement ϵ_5 per ion may be viewed as the perturbation due to the dipolar field of the H₂O molecules in the primary hydration layer. This perturbational energy ϵ_5 is not present in equation 1, but is a feature of the 'solvaton' model¹⁰.

(d). The hydrated gas phase species is transferred from vacuum to the bulk solvent to occupy the cavity. The relation $\epsilon_6 = \epsilon_{s,c} + \epsilon_{s,p}$, utilises CNDO/2 molecular orbital charges¹³ at different

atom centres of the polyatomic ion or molecule together with the adjusted values of atomic radii in hydrated state (equation 3).

(e). If the hydrated species is an ion, there will be further secondary hydration. For each of the 'n' number of proton-donor or -acceptor hydrating molecules in the primary layer, there would exist about the same number of hydrating molecules in the secondary hydration sheath. These additional 'n' molecules are made available from rupture of a tetrahedron (endothermic ϵ_1 per molecule) and involve a low net energy of interaction¹, ϵ_7 per molecule of water, for its orientation in the secondary layer. Thus, $n(\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_7)$ equals ϵ_{30} of Daudel expression. For neutral molecule there is little possibility² of any secondary hydration.

After thus identifying the different energy terms with the various Daudel terms qualitatively, it is now necessary to quantify the terms for final formulation of hydration energy which is

$$N\epsilon_s = N(\epsilon_{s0} + \epsilon_{sa} + \epsilon_{so} + \epsilon_{se} + \epsilon_{sp}) + N\epsilon_s = N[5\epsilon_1 + n\epsilon_2 + (5-n)\epsilon_3] + Nn\epsilon_4 + Nn(\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_7) + N\epsilon_6 + N\epsilon_8 \quad (2)$$

I II III IV V

where N is the Avogadro number.

Let us now consider the net contribution by the energy terms I, II and III (equation 2) for polyatomic ions and molecules separately. For ions $N\epsilon_1 = -N\epsilon_s = 6.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ (both by CNDO/2 and *ab initio* supermolecule approach), $N\epsilon_2 =$ enthalpy of vaporisation of water $= 9.8 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $N\epsilon_4 = -20 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ (*ab initio* supermolecule approach). $N\epsilon_7$, secondary hydration energy, can be reasoned out to be around $2 \sim 3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Thus for mono to pentahydration, the net energy contribution coming from I, II and III (Table 1) is about -3 kcal mol^{-1} which, being small, may be neglected.

TABLE 1

n	Energy in kcal g ion ⁻¹			
	I = $N\epsilon_{s0}$	II = $N\epsilon_{sa}$	III = $N\epsilon_{so}$	I + II + III
5	+79.5	-100.0	+18.0	-2.5
4	+63.6	-80.0	+14.4	-2.0
3	+47.7	-60.0	+10.8	-1.5
2	+31.8	-40.0	+7.2	-1.0
1	+16.2	-20.0	+3.6	-0.5

Therefore, for ions

$$\Delta E_{hydrn} = N\epsilon_s \approx N\epsilon_6 + N\epsilon_8$$

$$= -N \frac{1}{2} (1 - 1/D) \sum_{A,B} q_A q_B \Gamma_{AB} + 7.5/Z \quad (2a)$$

where the first term is the Born term equivalent^{1,2} in CNDO/2 theory and the second one the perturbational energy term*, Z being the valence of the ion.

For molecules, an analysis of the energy terms in equation 2 leads to (i) neglect of $N\epsilon_s$, (ii) neglect of secondary solvation $n(\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_7)$, (iii) anisotropic interaction energy $N\epsilon_{sa} = N\epsilon_{sa} = -8.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. The reason for neglecting the first is that for neutral molecules global charge transfer from the species to the hydration layer is not large rendering a very small effective polarisation due to perturbation (step 2c).

Since the secondary hydration of neutral molecules should be very small, the second factor is neglected. The third factor of anisotropic energy value for neutral molecules varies from -6 to $-11 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ of the hydrating molecules. It is much smaller than the corresponding ionic term ($-20 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and the average is around $-8.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Working within the framework of these assumptions, it is shown (Table 2) that the energy terms I and II of equation 2 (III has been set equal to zero) lead to definite but different endothermic values for uncharged molecules for mono- to pentahydration in the primary layer.

TABLE 2
Energy in kcal mol⁻¹

n	I	II	I + II
5	+79.5	-42.5	+37.0
4	+63.6	-34.0	+29.6
3	+47.7	-25.5	+22.2
2	+31.8	-17.0	+14.8
1	+16.2	-8.5	+7.7

Equation 2a and Table 1 enable us to write for polyatomic ions

$$\Delta E_{hydrn} = -627.1 \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{R_i} + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{R_{ij}} \right] \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) + 7.5/Z \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where the CNDO/2 molecular orbital atomic charges q_i, q_j 's, the effective atomic radii and interatomic distances R_i, R_{ij} 's in the hydrated state are in atomic units, and $D = 78.5$ at 25° .

The relations $R_i = r_i + pr_w$, and $R_{ij} = r_{ij} + qr_w$ are used in equation 3 where r_w is radius of water molecule (a.u.), and p and q are the radius adjustment factors, taken to be 0.5 and 1.0, respectively. A general CNDO/2 criterion for p, q values is set up later. The r_{ij}, R_i and R_{ij} data are internally calculated by the computer with instructions for original geometry and for r_i, r_j, p and q fed into it. Table 3 based on equation 3 comprises data for hydration energies of gas phase polyatomic ions.

We now turn to neutral molecules. Equation 2a and Table 2 permit us to write

$$\Delta E_{hydrn} = N\epsilon_6 + 7.4n \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where 'n' is the number of hydrating molecules (1 to 5) in the primary sheath. If the hydration

* Hydration energies of gas phase monovalent ions is around 70 to 100 kcal g ion⁻¹; perturbational energy can hardly exceed 5 to 10% of the actual. Hence, the setting of $N\epsilon_8 = 7.5/Z$ represents an average value.

TABLE 3

Polyatomic ion	Hydration energy kcal mol ⁻¹	
	Calcd. value from Eqn. (3) (1 a.u. = 627.1 kcal mol ⁻¹)	Literature value
Formate	-97.2	-
Fluoroformate	-101.65	-
Chloroformate	-91.06	-
Acetate	-90.56	-
Monofluoroacetate	-88.82	-92.60
Difluoroacetate	-90.95	-86.60 ^a
Trifluoroacetate	-95.86	-
Monochloroacetate	-86.1	-88.20 ^a
Dichloroacetate	-83.5	-83.10 ^a
Propionate	-88.40	-
Ammonium	-81.29	-(72.5 ± 5.5) ^{b, c}
Nitrate	-78.59	-75.01 ^b
Nitrite	-88.5	-96.75 ^b
Chlorate	-87.24	-83.14 ^b
Sulphate	-254.6	-253.0 ^b
Sulphite	-328.1	-
Bisulphide	-84.52	-79.55 ^b
Thiocyanate	-76.01	-74.06 ^b
Carbonate	-317.1	-313.9 ^b
Methoxide	-84.29	-
Ethoxide	-78.34	-
Isopropoxide	-73.93	-
t-Butoxide	-70.49	-

^aP. Haberfield and A. K. Rakshit, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 4393.

^bRef. 8. ^cRef. 7.

number 'n' obtained by 'supermolecule approach' for any organic molecule be taken to be the same for other members of the same class (such as open chain carboxylic acids or amides or esters), then ΔE_{hydrn} can be easily evaluated (Table 4) using the Born type expression with CNDO/2 charge distribution.

$$\Delta E_{hydrn} = \left\{ -627.1 \left[\left(\sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{2r_i} + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) \right] + 7.4n \right\} \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

In equation 5 one is to use the same r_i and r_{ij} as in the equilibrium configuration and no adjustment in radius value is made since the perturbational energy ($N\epsilon_s$) has already been set equal to zero. A few trials show that the results can also be computed with the help of Born type expression alone where radius adjustments are made, $R_i = r_i + pr_w$, and $R_{ij} = r_{ij} + qr_w$, with p, q values being 1 and 2, respectively.

$$\Delta E_{hydrn} = N\epsilon_s (\text{adjusted}) = -627.1 \left[\left(\sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{r_i + pr_w} + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij} + qr_w} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

TABLE 4

Molecule	$N\epsilon_s$	7.4n	Hydration energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)		
			Calculated from Eqn. (5)	Calculated from Eqn. (6)	Literature value
Formic acid	-36.3	29.6	-6.7	-12.47	-9.97 ^a
Fluoroformic acid	-60.14	37.0	-23.14	-22.08	-
Chloroformic acid	-47.16	29.6	-17.56	-16.54	-
Acetic acid	-42.33	29.6	-12.73	-14.74	-10.20 ^a
Monofluoroacetic acid	-49.0	29.6	-19.4	-15.73	-17.04
Difluoroacetic acid	-60.14	37.0*	-23.14	-19.94	-17.89 ^o
Trifluoroacetic acid	-76.52	37.0*	-39.52	-26.78	-
Monochloroacetic acid	-48.35	29.6	-18.75	-15.97	-15.16 ^o
Dichloroacetic acid	-45.34	29.6	-15.83	-14.75	-16.16 ^o
Formamide	-38.50	29.6	-8.9	-13.34	≈ -13.36 ^a
Acetamide	-43.14	29.6	-13.54	-14.91	-12.03 ^a
Propionamide	-43.46	29.6	-13.86	-15.30	-18.11 ^a
Methyl formate	-27.47	22.2**	-5.27	-11.25	-8.16 ^a
Ethyl formate	-28.23	22.2**	-6.08	-11.83	-8.33 ^a
Methyl acetate	-35.05	22.2**	-12.85	-13.69	≈ -12.02 ^a
Methyl alcohol	-13.36	11.1 [†]	-2.26	-4.07	-11.38 ^a -10.98 ^a
Ethyl alcohol	-13.48	11.1 [†]	-2.38	-4.45	-12.22 ^a
Isopropyl alcohol	-14.61	11.1 [†]	-3.5	-4.91	-14.33 (20°) ^{a, b} -13.33 (B.P.) ^{a, b}
t-Butyl alcohol	-14.8	11.1 [†]	-3.7	-5.12	-14.43 (25°) ^{a, b} -12.71 (B.P.) ^{a, b}

*For fluoroformic, difluoroacetic and trifluoroacetic acid, n=5. **For esters, n=3. †For alcohol set, due to low energy of interaction of one of the two hydrating units, the hydration number 'n' has been set equal to 1.5.

^a"Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", ed. R. C. Weast, 59th. ed., 2nd Printing, C. R. C. Press, Florida, 1979, C-730, C-722, C-723; "International Critical Tables", Vol. 5, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1929, pp. 136 (Table C), 148 (Table 1). ^bJ. A. Riddick and E. E. Toops, Jr., "Organic Solvents", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1955. ^oP. Haberfield and A. K. Rakshit, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 4393.

TABLE 5—CHARGE DISTRIBUTION CRITERION FOR CLASSIFICATION INTO DIFFERENT (p, q) PAIRS

Species Molecule Ion	Amount of (+) ve charge on the central atom () in a.u.	Amount of total (-) ve charge of the atoms on the surface of the sphere in a.u.*	Surface density of (-) charge on the surface of the sphere in a.u./sq. Å	$\rho \times 10^3$	p, q values
CO ₃ ²⁻	0.4032 (C)	2.4032 (O, O, O)	0.1131	28.05	0.5, 1
NCS ⁻	0.1118 (C)	1.1118 (N, S)	0.0365	32.63	0.5, 1
HCOO ⁻ (COO ⁻)	0.3894 (C)	1.1606 (O, O)	0.0591	15.17	0.5, 1
FCH ₂ COO ⁻ (COO ⁻)	0.3408 (C)	1.1150 (O, O)	0.0550	16.13	0.5, 1
ClCH ₂ COO ⁻ (COO ⁻)	0.3681 (C)	1.1052 (O, O)	0.0545	14.80	0.5, 1
CH ₃ O ⁻	0.1594 (C)	1.1594 (O, H, H, H)	0.0464	29.10	0.5, 1
ClO ₂ ⁻	0.3893 (Cl)	1.3893 (O, O, O)	0.0448	11.51	0.5, 1**
NO ₃ ⁻	0.6361 (N)	1.6361 (O, O, O)	0.0877	13.79	1, 2**
FCOO ⁻	0.5214 (C)	1.1585 (O, O)	0.0590	11.31	0.5, 1**
SO ₃ ²⁻	1.1223 (S)	3.1223 (O, O, O, O)	0.1200	10.67	1, 2
HCOOH (-COOH)	0.3721 (C)	0.5487 (H, O, O)	0.0236	6.34	1, 2
CH ₃ COOH (-COOH)	0.3930 (C)	0.6769 (C, O, O)	0.0233	5.93	1, 2
FCH ₂ COOH (-COOH)	0.3684 (C)	0.4112 (C, O, O)	0.0142	3.84	1, 2
ClCH ₂ COOH (-COOH)	0.4140 (C)	0.5629 (C, O, O)	0.0194	4.68	1, 2
CH ₃ CH ₂ OH	0.1663 (C)	0.3381 (C, H, H, O)	0.0113	6.81	1, 2
CH ₃ CONH ₂ (-CONH ₂)	0.3677 (C)	0.6881 (C, N, O)	0.0243	6.61	1, 2
CH ₃ COOCH ₃ (-COOCH ₃)	0.4007 (C)	0.6425 (C, O, O)	0.0227	5.66	1, 2

Species having (p, q) values (0.5, 1): Ions: formate, fluoroformate, chloroformate, acetate, monofluoroacetate, difluoroacetate, trifluoroacetate, monochloroacetate, dichloroacetate, propionate, methoxide, ethoxide, isopropoxide, t-butoxide, chlorate, thiocyanate, nitrite, sulphite, carbonate, bisulphide.

Species having (p, q) values (1, 2): Ions: nitrate, sulphate; Molecules: acids: formic, fluoroformic, chloroformic, acetic, monofluoroacetic, difluoroacetic, trifluoroacetic, monochloroacetic, dichloroacetic, propionic; alcohols: methyl, ethyl, isopropyl, t-butyl; amides: formamide, acetamide, propionamide; esters: methyl formate, ethyl formate, methyl acetate.

*Ligand atoms in parenthesis. **Buffer zone, trials with (p, q) needed.

The relation 6 removes the necessity of any preknowledge of 'n', the hydration number in the primary layer.

Table 4 speaks for itself. However, the calculated values of hydration energy for the alcohol set seem to be off by about -8.0 to -10.0 kcal/mol⁻¹. But the calculated values refer to monomeric forms of alcohols whereas the literature values, evaluated from the thermodynamic data of the relevant enthalpy terms, are not exclusive of the effect of existence of dimers. Hence, the apparent deviations in case of alcohols, shown in Table 4 are largely illusory.

We would complete our discussion by setting up a charge distribution criterion for assigning (p, q) values in radius adjustment. We have seen that only two pairs of values, (0.5, 1.0) and (1.0, 2.0), can cover a wide selection of ions and molecules. We assume a sphere of effective radius drawn around the central atom of the ion (such as N atom in NO₃⁻) and compute the surface density of the charges due to directly linked ligand atoms if these charges were smeared on the spherical surface. For neutral molecule, one is to choose that one as

the central atom the neighbourhood of which is likely to be the zone of primary hydration (e.g. carbon atom of the carboxylic group of an acid). For any particular species, the ratio ρ , of this surface charge density to the central charge is calculated and few such sample data (recorded as $\rho \times 10^3$) are given in Table 5.

When the ratio ($\rho \times 10^3$) > (12.5 ± 1.5), the (p, q) pair are (0.5, 1.0) and where it is less the (p, q) pair are (1.0, 2.0). There are a few species (e.g. NO₃⁻, fluoroformate etc.) for which the values fall in buffer zone (viz. 12.5 ± 1.5). Trial calculations made with the one or the other (p, q) pair show one of these two to conform to literature values.

Below Table 5 there appear different species (ions and molecules) which are thus classified under the two (p, q) types. This criterion cuts across the division of species into ions and molecules and accounts for using the same (p, q) values for SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, acetic acid and alcohols. This charge criterion, therefore, helps in bringing into order much of the confusion over radius adjustment of ions and molecules in solution.

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